

ACCELERATION OF SEXUAL MATURATION OF COMMON CARP BY ACCELERATION OF GROWTH IN CAGES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the spring - autumn of 2023, yearlings of common carp were grown in floating cages in the Tuyabuguz reservoir in Uzbekistan, fed with balanced high-protein feeds Aller Aqua, which caused rapid growth of carp and rapid maturation. Already in winter, 2-summerlings of both sexes reached their first sexual maturation with a standard body length of 41 - 46 cm (in pond fish hatcheries, carp reaches sexual maturation at the age of 3). Absolute fecundity in January was 1072.8 - 3008.4 (on average 1773.2) thousand eggs.

Keywords: carp, *Cyprinus carpio*, growth, maturation, cages, Uzbekistan

Carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) - a popular pond fish farming object in Uzbekistan, it is currently one of the few promising objects for intensive cultivation in cages in local conditions. In open water bodies and in fish ponds, carp reaches its first sexual maturity at the age of 3-4 years, when it reaches a standard body length of 32 cm or more (Salikhov et al., 2003, Kamilov, Kurbanov, 2009). In cages, high-protein feed is used for carp growth. It is known that the rate of maturation in fish is positively related to fish growth (Kamilov et al., 2019). In this regard, the goal of this work was chosen - to determine whether faster carp growth in cages will cause significantly faster maturation in the conditions of Uzbekistan, which will create new prospects for the formation of broodstocks of this species in the country. Uzbekistan is located in the southern zone of the temperate climate with sharp temperature changes between seasons: hot summer (daytime temperatures from the second half of May to the end of September remain above 30 ° C) and relatively cold winter (the average monthly air temperature in January in Tashkent varies from -2 to -4 ° C). The average daily water temperature warms up above 14 ° C (the beginning of the growth of warm-water fish) in mid-April, drops below 14 ° C (the end of the growing season) at the end of October. The period of rapid growth of carp (the average daily water temperature is above 20-22 ° C) is about 4.5-5 months. (Kamilov et al., 2018). Carp in ponds are grown to a marketable weight for two years: in the first year up to 20-25 g, in the second year - up to 1000 g or more. The work was carried out at the Fishberg fish farm on the Tuyabuguz reservoir in the Tashkent region of Uzbekistan in the middle reaches of the Angren River, a large tributary of the Syr Darya River. In April 2023, one-

year-old carp (after wintering) from a pond fish hatchery (20-30 g) were stocked into 4 floating fish cages (each 100 m³). They were fed with balanced carp feed "Aller Aqua" (for carp) (protein content 33%), the diet was determined depending on the water temperature and the size of the fish according to the recommendations of the manufacturer (3% of the total fish biomass). In January 2024, 40 random carp individuals were examined: the standard body length, total body weight were measured, sex and maturity stage were determined visually, gonad weight, absolute fertility of females (Pravdin, 1966).

The dynamics of the average daily water temperature in the Tuyabuguz reservoir is shown in Figure 1. The level of dissolved oxygen in the water of the cages was at the level of 5.9 - 6.76 mg/l throughout the growing season, the pH of the water was 7.3 - 8.8, the total dissolved ammonia nitrogen in the water fluctuated between 0.00 - 0.01 mg/l. By the end of November, the fish productivity of the cages reached 43 kg/m³.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of water temperature of the Tuyabuguz reservoir, 2023 y

The sample included females with a standard length of 35–40 (37.9 on average) cm, with a total body weight of 890–1691 (1323.9) g. There were no differences in size between the sexes of the carp (the average body weight of females and males was 1328.5 and 1316.3 g, respectively). The ratio of females to males in the sample was 1.6: 1. At the same time, the females already had a noticeable abdomen, which is a secondary characteristic of sexually mature carp. Note that these are 2-year-old females.

Of the 16 males, only one (39.0 cm and 1447 g) had gonads at stages II–III, the gonad weight was 16 g, the maturity coefficient was 1.1%. The remaining males had gonads at maturity stage IV, with a gonad weight of 16-103 (65.5 on average) g. The maturity coefficient for these males at the end of December was 2.2-7.8 (5.7)%. The overwhelming majority of females (25 out of 26 specimens) had gonads at maturity stage IV. The females had a total body length of 41-46

cm, a standard length of 35-40 cm, and a total body weight of 992-1691 g. The gonad weight at maturity stage IV in January for these females varied within the range of 67-992 (187.385) g. It was found that larger females had greater gonad weight, but the strength of the relationship was not high ($r = 0.38$) (Fig. 2). The absolute fertility of females in January varied from 1072.8 to 3008.4 (1773.2) thousand eggs.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the gonad mass of sexually mature two-year-old females on their body length.

Carp in Uzbekistan is reproduced by stimulating maturation with gonadotropic substances in females aged 4-5 years (standard length 55-70 cm), which reach their first sexual maturity at the age of 3 years. It is known that the maturation rate is positively related to the speed of fish. In cages, as in an intensive system, balanced high-protein feeds are used, which causes accelerated growth of the generation. The results we obtained are in good agreement with the literature (Kamilov et al, 2020), since Uzbekistan is located in the south of the temperate climate. Here, carp, despite growth cessations for wintering, have fairly rapid growth and rapid maturation. At the same time, keeping fish in cages provides new material for this fairly well-studied issue. Thus, in 2023, when cultivating carp at the Fishberg fish farm in the Tuyabuguz reservoir, where we conducted experiments, fish farmers fed the fish with balanced high-protein feeds and achieved rapid growth. At the same time, the cages were stocked with standard fish seeding material - yearlings from fish hatcheries in the Tashkent region. A significant part of the fish of the generation grew to a standard length of more than 32 cm and a total body weight of more than 2.5 - 3 kg. By autumn, these were two-year-olds. However, already in September, our autopsies showed that such fish at the age of 2+ (and their share was subjectively more than 60% in the generation) already had gonads at a well-defined III stage of maturity, i.e. by

spring, at the age of 2 years, they will be sexually mature. This opens up great prospects for significant optimization of carp reproduction in Uzbekistan for its increasing reproduction under the conditions of integrated water use.

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